

Case Report

Yoga Prana Vidya Healing for Rapid Recovery in Acute Neurological Collapse: A Paediatric Case Report of a 13 years old boy

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Article Info

Keywords: Neurological collapse, Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy, Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®

Received: 03.02.2026;

Accepted: 03.03.2026;

Published: 09.03.2026

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Abstract

Background: Acute neurological collapse in adolescents, presenting as sudden unconsciousness, abnormal body movements, and seizure-like episodes, requires urgent medical evaluation. Conventional investigations may fail to identify a clear aetiology. Complementary therapies such as Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) have been reported to support rapid recovery in unexplained conditions.

Case Presentation: A 13-year-old male student, presented with sudden unconsciousness, body twisting, and abnormal vocalizations on December 7, 2022. He was admitted to a Multi-Specialist Hospital and placed under intensive care. Despite three days of observation the medical team could not conclude, though haematology and biochemistry were normal, except for lymphocytosis. MRI brain revealed mild cortical hyperintensities, interpreted as sequelae of hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy. Brucella IgM positivity suggested possible infection.

Intervention: On December 9, 2022, Yoga Prana Vidya healing was initiated by a YPV Certified healer who conducted two sessions of 30 minutes each, focusing on YPV psychotherapy, internal organ cleansing, and brain chakras energy balancing.

Results: Within four hours of the first session of the YPV healing, the patient regained consciousness, though with mild headache. After the second session on the same day, he returned to normal functioning. He was discharged the following day, with no residual neurological deficits.

Conclusion: This case highlights the potential role of YPV healing as an adjunctive modality in acute unexplained neurological collapse. While medical investigations suggested possible infectious or metabolic causes, rapid recovery following YPV intervention warrants further systematic study. YPV healing may offer supportive benefits in acute neurological conditions where conventional medicine shows limited immediate efficacy.

1. Introduction

Acute neurological collapse in adolescents is a medical emergency requiring urgent evaluation. Common causes include epilepsy, metabolic encephalopathy, infections, and hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) [1–3]. MRI findings of cortical hyperintensities often suggest

sequelae of hypoxic injury or metabolic dysfunction [4, 5].

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) is an integrative energy-based healing system combining physical exercises, breathing techniques, and energy healing by a healer (cleansing and energising protocols). Previous reports suggest YPV may support recovery in cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and psychological distress [6–8]. Its application in acute neurological collapse remains underexplored.

2. Case Presentation

A 13-year-old male student, presented on December 7, 2022, with sudden unconsciousness, abnormal body twisting, and oral secretions. He was admitted to a Multi-Specialist Hospital, under ICU observation.

Medical Investigations revealed:

- Overall haematology and biochemistry are within normal limits.
- Absolute lymphocytosis noted, which may correlate with infection.
- Brucella IgM positive → Suggests recent brucellosis infection, requiring clinical correlation and confirmatory testing.
- MRI brain (Annexure 1) shows mild diffuse hyperintensities, possibly metabolic or infectious; follow-up imaging advised.
- No evidence of hepatitis B or HIV infection.
- No acute inflammatory markers (CRP normal).
- Coagulation profile normal.

Despite three days of medical observation, no improvement was noted.

YPV Intervention: The patient's father approached a Certified YPV Healer who initiated healing intervention on December 9, 2022 (third day in the hospital). Two YPV healing sessions on that day (30 minutes each) were conducted, focusing on brain, chakras healing, and YPV psychotherapy.

Details of the intervention:

- (A) YPV Psychotherapy
- (B) Internal organ technique
- (C) Clean entire brain and upper chakras and appropriate energising. Special cleaning of brain.

Details of healing sessions

- Total number of healings, 2 healings on this day
- Total time half an hour per healing

Patient progress with patient response

Patient responded well after giving one session of healing. He became fully conscious after 4 hours, but he reported some headache. After one more healing session on the same day he became fully normal.

3. Results Summary

- Within four hours of the first healing, patient regained consciousness.
- After the second session, he was normal, with headache resolved fully.
- He was shifted to the ward from ICU, the following day, with no neurological deficits.
- He was kept under observation and discharged after 3 days.
- Testimony of patient's father (Annexure 2) confirmed rapid recovery, that surprised attending physicians.

4. Discussion

This case demonstrates the potential role of YPV healing in acute unexplained neurological collapse. While Brucella infection and MRI findings suggested possible underlying pathology, conventional management alone did not yield improvement. Rapid recovery following YPV intervention suggests an adjunctive therapeutic effect.

YPV has been reported to improve outcomes in cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and psychological distress [6–10]. Energy healing may influence autonomic regulation, stress response, and neurophysiological balance [11–13]. In this case, YPV may have facilitated rapid restoration of consciousness and neurological stability. Further controlled studies are required to validate these findings and explore mechanisms.

A similar case of acute demyelinating illness successfully healed by YPV healing was reported by Kataria et al (2025) [14].

The topic of medically unexplained neurological symptoms in children and adolescents was studied by [15] and concluded that over half of adolescents and families expressed that their experience to multi-disciplinary team assessment was helpful. Despite persistence of symptoms in the majority, their two-year outcome data from the studied cohort shows improvement in daily activities and participation in two-thirds of the sample [15].

5. Conclusion

YPV healing may serve as a supportive adjunct in acute neurological collapse, particularly when conventional medicine shows limited immediate efficacy. This case highlights the need for integrative approaches in unexplained neurological emergencies.

Article Information

Acknowledgments: The authors thank the patient's family for sharing case details on condition of anonymity. Our thanks are also to Sri Ramana Trust (Thally-635118) for permission to use their copyright terms Yoga Prana Vidya System ® and YPV®.

Author Contributions: Ritesh Kataria, Urvashi Kataria: Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing – review & editing; Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri: Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Funding / Financial Support: The authors received no external funding.

Competing Interests: Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical Approval: Not Applicable

Informed Consent: Informed consent from patient and his family obtained.

Data Availability Statement: Data available on reasonable request.

Clinical Trial Registration: Not applicable.

Reporting Guidelines Statement: Not applicable.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

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Annexure 1: MRI dated 07 December 2022

MULTI-SPECIALTY HOSPITALS

Patient Name	[REDACTED]	MRN / Visit No.	SHL0000472151/TP-001
Age / Gender	12 Years/MALE	Admission No. /Bed	ADSHI.221200163 / 206
Ref. by Doctor	Hetal Parikh	Report Date	Dec 7, 2022
Bill No.		Bill Date	

MRI Brain Plain With Contrast

Department of Interventional & Diagnostic Radiology

INVESTIGATION: MRI OF BRAIN WITH CONTRAST.
 AXIAL T1W, T2W, SAGITTAL T2W & CORONAL FLAIR, POST CONTRAST AXIAL SAGITTAL AND CORONAL IMAGES THROUGH BRAIN HAS BEEN OBTAINED ON 1.5 TESLA 16 CHANNELS SYSTEM WITH HIGH STRENGTH GRADIENTS.

Possible mild T2 and FLAIR hyperintensity noted involving cortex of supratentorial brain, cerebellum and bilateral basal ganglia. No evidence of significant restricted diffusion. Ventricular system appears within normal limits. There is no shift of midline structures. No evidence of intra-cerebral or extra-cerebral haematoma. No evidence of supra-tentorial or infra-tentorial SOL. Brain-stem structures and cerebellar hemispheres appear normal. Post contrast study does not reveal any additional information.
Mild mucosal thickening seen in left frontal, ethmoid and sphenoid sinus.

OPINION:

- Possible mild T2 and FLAIR hyperintensity involving cortex of supratentorial brain, cerebellum and bilateral basal ganglia. No evidence of significant restricted diffusion. Suggested follow up study to look for temporal evolution to rule out possibility of metabolic cause.
- No evidence of abnormal enhancement on post contrast study.

Annexure 2: Feedback from Patient's father

I am .xxxxx. I want to say about an incident that happened to my 13 year-old son. Suddenly one day, something happened in his body. We don't know what happened. . . like you see in horror movies. . . his body started getting twisted, fluids started coming from his mouth. We then admitted him in a hospital in Ahmedabad. A doctor and his team admitted him in ICU and kept on observation. Even after being in the ICU we couldn't see any improvement in his condition. His body continued to be in twisted condition and strange sounds were coming from his mouth. Our entire family was getting worried. At that stage a friend of mine asked me if I knew about Healing. I knew nothing about healing. Afterwards, my friend said he knew a friend who is a healer, who can heal even a small illness or a big illness. We didn't know what to do. On one hand my son's medical treatment was going on, on the other hand there was no improvement. So I decided to experiment with this healing. I took healer's number and called him. I explained about the situation, everything my boy was going through, and I sent his photo. The healer promised me that he would start healing the boy and within 24 hours the boy would become normal. And no need to worry. With that hope I was also praying and blessing. The Healer conducted healing sessions . We were not clear of what healing is and how it works. . . so we were sceptical being not sure of the outcome. We didn't know what magic the healing did, my boy became normal within 24 hours. I want to say that even now the doctor was also surprised, and had no clue to how the boy recovered with healing. The doctors kept the boy under observation for 3 days, yet they could not even find out the exact cause of the sickness. I am also clue less as to how the healer and his team managed to take out the illness from my boy's body. My boy is now back to normal in every respect. Thank you Healer and your team.